

PSYCHOPHYSIOLOGY OF STRESS CAN BE DIMINISHED BY OBSERVATION OF GRAPHICAL PATTERNS

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6346822>

Katamanova Djemilya Lemarovna

Director of ANO "Center for the Study of Living Systems", Russian Federation

Sataieva Tatiana Pavlovna

Dr. Sci, Professor of V.I. Vernadsky Crimean Federal University, Russian Federation

Summary: Stress is a state of the body characterized by emotional and physical stress caused by the influence of various adverse factors. The concept of stress implies a situation that causes the need for adaptation of the body. The aim of the research was to approve a methodology that helps to reduce the level of daily stress and emotional stress that affects the psychophysiological state of a person. The experiment involved 15 relatively healthy students of both sexes aged 18 to 25 years who were working as medical volunteers. After classes the students were given to complete a graphical task. Before and after completing the experimental task, the subject was asked to pass psychological tests.

Keywords: stress, graphical task, electrophysiology.

In past years the problem of information stress is one of the topical issues of modern society. Our century is considered the century of the "information explosion". Stress is the process of adapting to circumstances that disrupt or threaten to imbalance the body [1]. A little stress or the optimal level of stress is necessary for a person's activity to overcome the obstacles that arise on the way to the routine goal achievement. This mobilizing, energizing stress makes a person active, ready for action, increasing the strength and speed of his physical and mental reactions, sharpening attention, memory, mental activity, etc.

Boredom, stagnation, a routine life devoid of pleasure is a strong stress that people tend to overcome with the help of movies, games, alcohol and thousands of other entertainments. However, there is a danger that in the pursuit of "adrenaline dose" one can step over the line separating "good stress" (Hans Selye's term) from "bad". Therefore, stress cannot be avoided, human has to live with it and get along, be able to cope with it. Certain methods of correcting the psychophysiological state are often used for "peaceful" interaction with daily stress, [2, 3].

The incoming information flow nowadays is so great that the brain begins to work actively trying to "sort it out". This differentiation manifests itself in the stress of the brain processing information. In this case mainly the left hemisphere is involved. At the same time, the right one is idle, thereby violating the interhemispheric balance. There is a deficit in the natural balance, which is characterized by depression [4].

The target of the research is to approve a methodology that helps to reduce the level of daily stress and emotional stress that affects the psychophysiological state of a person.

Material and Methods. The experiment involved 15 relatively healthy students of both sexes aged 18 to 25 years who were working as medical volunteers. Written informed consent was obtained from all subjects for the participation in the experiment. After classes the students were given to complete a graphical task. Before and after completing the experimental task, the subject was asked to pass psychological tests: a visual analogue scale of the situational emotional state and the Spielberger-Khanin scale of personal and situational anxiety, STAI. The experimental antistress task was to simultaneously trace the symmetrical plastic reliefs of the certain spirals and curves with the fingertips of both hands for 5 minutes (RF patent No. 149915 dated 30.08.2013 "Method for harmonizing the functions of the cerebral hemispheres").

The electroencephalogram was recorded using the encephalograph Encephalo "Poly 6" for 1 minute before and after the experimental task, 16 electrodes were used and located according to the international scheme "10-20". All quantitative data were expressed as mean \pm SD. $P < 0.05$ was regarded as statistically significant.

Results. We detected the negative psychophysiological changes under the influence of routine educational stress which affected the autonomic balance. Stress had significantly affected the level of mental activity and induced the reactive anxiety caused by the effects of stress hormones on nonspecific systems and autonomic centers located in the structures of the limbic-reticular complex of the brain.

However, the electrophysiological study showed that after completing the graphical spiral task, the subjects demonstrated an increase in the alpha rhythm in the occipital O2 lead, which can evidence the relaxation of the visual analyzer and the optimization of the perception mechanisms. A significant increase in the power of the theta rhythm in both hemispheres of the brain showed the improvement in the function of the optic analyzer associated with a decrease in the level of anxiety.

In the analysis of the electroencephalogram obtained after performing a sensory-tactile task with closed eyes there was demonstration of an active displacement of interhemispheric connections from the frontal region to the prefrontal and post- and precentral regions of the brain. Such displacement can appear during the state of visual and mental relaxation.

The interhemispheric connections formed by the alpha rhythm were redistributed in such a way that the Fp 1, F 4 and P 4 connections were activated. This indicates the manifestation of a relaxing effect on the more active left hemisphere (which was considered as active, since all the subjects were right-handed), which indicates that there is a decrease in cognitive load, and the extinction of internal dialogue.

Conclusion. Stressors are stimulators that arise in a situation that causes stress in an individual. They can be discrete and continuous. Many studies of discrete stressors are devoted to the study of the main (key) life events, such as death, serious illness, retirement, etc . These are relatively rare events, but the individual must adapt to them. Continuous stressors are defined as continuous and continuous problems in an individual's daily activities. Despite the growing interest in the problem of everyday stress in recent decades, the number of studies correlating psychological parameters and features for the management of everyday stress remain quite scarce. We have developed and tested the affordable method for reducing the level of stress in medical students, which turned out to be effective in changing the psychophysiological manifestation of stress, since the level of stressful activity is directly related to the degree of personal anxiety. It has been proved that the fulfillment of the experimental task has a relaxing effect on the subjects and reliably reduces the level of personal anxiety.

REFERENCES:

1. Bourbonnais R, Brisson C, Vézina M. Long-term effects of an intervention on psychosocial work factors among healthcare professionals in a hospital setting. *Occupational and Environmental Medicine* 2011;68(7):479-86.
2. Gardner B, Rose J, Mason O, Tyler P, Cushway D. Cognitive therapy and behavioural coping in the management of work-related stress: An intervention study. *Work and Stress* 2005;19(2):137-52.
3. Jones MC, Johnston DW. Evaluating the impact of a worksite stress management programme for distressed students: a randomised controlled trial. *Psychology and Health* 2000;15:689-706.

4. Lökk J, Arnetz B. Impact of management change and an intervention program on health care personnel. *Psychotherapy and Psychosomatics* 2000;69(2):79-85.

